

CONGRUENCES MODULO 512 FOR THE OVERPARTITION FUNCTION

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Abstract

Let $\bar{p}(n)$ denote the number of overpartitions of n . Many scholars have investigated congruence properties modulo powers of 2 that hold for $\bar{p}(n)$. In this paper, we establish two infinite families of congruences modulo 512 for $\bar{p}(n)$ by employing some q -series techniques. For instance, one result proved in the present paper is that for any $\alpha \geq 0$ and $n \geq 0$,

$$\bar{p}(3^{8\alpha+7}(24n+5)) \equiv 0 \pmod{512}.$$

Finally, we conjecture that there are two infinite families of congruences modulo high powers of 2 satisfied by $\bar{p}(n)$.

1. Introduction

A *partition* of a positive integer n is a weakly decreasing sequence of positive integers whose sum equals n . To provide combinatorial proofs for some well-known q -series identities, Corteel and Lovejoy [4] introduced the concept of overpartitions. An *overpartition* of n is a partition of n in which the first occurrence of a number may be overlined. Let $\bar{p}(n)$ denote the number of overpartitions of n , and we define that $\bar{p}(0) = 1$. From [4], the generating function for $\bar{p}(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(n)q^n = \frac{(-q; q)_{\infty}}{(q; q)_{\infty}} = \frac{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}}{(q; q)_{\infty}^2}, \quad (1)$$

where we always assume that q is a complex number such that $|q| < 1$ and adopt the following standard notation:

$$(a; q)_{\infty} = \prod_{k=0}^{\infty} (1 - aq^k).$$

In 2004, Mahlburg [12] proved that

$$\lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\#\{0 \leq n < X : \bar{p}(n) \equiv 0 \pmod{64}\}}{X} = 1.$$

He further conjectured that for any positive integer k ,

$$\lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\#\{0 \leq n < X : \bar{p}(n) \equiv 0 \pmod{2^k}\}}{X} = 1. \tag{2}$$

The above conjecture, if true, would be a powerful arithmetic density property modulo powers of 2. Kim [10] and Xiong [14] later confirmed (2) for the cases $k = 7$ and $k = 8$. Although Mahlburg’s conjecture is still open for any $k \geq 9$, it reveals that there are numerous congruence properties modulo powers of 2 for $\bar{p}(n)$.

Many scholars have studied congruence relations modulo 2 for the function $\bar{p}(n)$. For instance, Fortin et al. [7], and Hirschhorn et al. [8] have established the 2-, 3- and 4-dissections of the generating function of $\bar{p}(n)$, enabling the derivation of certain congruences modulo 4 and 8. In particular, they deduced the following three Ramanujan-like identities:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(2n+1)q^n &= 2 \frac{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}^2 (q^8; q^8)_{\infty}^2}{(q; q)_{\infty}^4 (q^4; q^4)_{\infty}}, \\ \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(4n+3)q^n &= 8 \frac{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty} (q^4; q^4)_{\infty}^6}{(q; q)_{\infty}^8}, \\ \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(8n+7)q^n &= 64 \frac{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}^{22}}{(q; q)_{\infty}^{23}}. \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Hirschhorn et al. [8] further conjectured that

$$\bar{p}(\ell n + r) = \begin{cases} 0 \pmod{4} & \text{if } \ell \equiv \pm 3 \pmod{8}, \\ 0 \pmod{8} & \text{if } \ell \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{8}, \end{cases}$$

where ℓ is an odd prime and r is a quadratic nonresidue modulo ℓ . This conjecture was subsequently proved by Kim [11].

Additionally, Kim [11] got a complete characterization of $\bar{p}(n)$ modulo 8. Andersen [1] considered several Hecke-type congruences modulo small powers of 2 for $\bar{p}(n)$. Later, several authors have established Ramanujan-type congruences modulo 16, 32, and 64 for $\bar{p}(n)$; see, for example, [3, 5, 17]. Chen et al. [3] demonstrated that $\bar{p}(n)$ satisfies congruences modulo powers of 2, while Du et al. [6] derived several congruence families modulo small powers of 2 satisfied by $\bar{p}(n)$. Tang [13] also deduced numerous internal congruences and congruences modulo powers of 2 for $\bar{p}(n)$. Yang et al. [16] proved several infinite families of congruences modulo 256 that hold for $\bar{p}(n)$. They derived that for any $\alpha \geq 0$ and $n \geq 0$,

$$\bar{p}(3^{4\alpha+3}(24n+5)) \equiv \bar{p}(3^{4\alpha+3}(24n+13)) \equiv 0 \pmod{256}. \tag{4}$$

Shortly thereafter, Yao [18] derived several infinite families of congruences modulo 64 and 1024 for $\bar{p}(n)$. She proved that for any $\alpha \geq 0$ and $n \geq 0$,

$$\bar{p}(3^{16\alpha+15}(24n+5)) \equiv \bar{p}(3^{16\alpha+15}(24n+13)) \equiv 0 \pmod{1024}. \tag{5}$$

Recently, Xue and Yao [15] further established many explicit congruences modulo 2048 for $\bar{p}(n)$. They proved that for any $\alpha \geq 0$ and $n \geq 0$,

$$\bar{p}(3^{32\alpha+31}(24n+5)) \equiv \bar{p}(3^{32\alpha+31}(24n+13)) \equiv 0 \pmod{2048}. \tag{6}$$

Therefore, it is natural to ask whether there exist congruence families modulo 512 similar to (4)-(6) for $\bar{p}(n)$. The following theorem says that there is a positive answer for this question.

Theorem 1. *For any $\alpha \geq 0$ and $n \geq 0$,*

$$\bar{p}(3^{8\alpha+7}(24n+5)) \equiv \bar{p}(3^{8\alpha+7}(24n+13)) \equiv 0 \pmod{512}. \tag{7}$$

Motivated by (4)-(7), we pose the following conjecture.

Conjecture 1. *For any $m \geq 2$, $\alpha \geq 0$, and $n \geq 0$,*

$$\bar{p}(3^{2^m\alpha+2^m-1}(24n+5)) \equiv \bar{p}(3^{2^m\alpha+2^m-1}(24n+13)) \equiv 0 \pmod{2^{m+6}}. \tag{8}$$

2. Proof of Theorem 1

In this section, we give a proof of Theorem 1. Before stating it, we collect the following important lemma. For the sake of convenience, we write

$$E(q) = (q; q)_\infty.$$

Lemma 1. *We have*

$$\frac{E(q^2)^2}{E(q)} = \frac{E(q^6)E(q^9)^2}{E(q^3)E(q^{18})} + q \frac{E(q^{18})^2}{E(q^9)}, \tag{9}$$

$$\frac{E(q^6)^3E(q^9)^6}{E(q^3)^3E(q^{18})^3} = \frac{E(q^6)^8E(q^9)}{E(q^3)^4E(q^{18})^2} - q^3 \frac{E(q^{18})^6}{E(q^9)^3}, \tag{10}$$

$$\frac{E(q)}{E(q^2)^2} = \frac{E(q^3)^2E(q^9)^3}{E(q^6)^6} - q \frac{E(q^3)^3E(q^{18})^3}{E(q^6)^7} + q^2 \frac{E(q^3)^4E(q^{18})^6}{E(q^6)^8E(q^9)^3}. \tag{11}$$

The identity (9) is from [2, p. 49, Corollary], while (10) and (11) come from [9, Lemmas 2.1 and 2.2].

Now, we turn to prove Theorem 1.

Proof of Theorem 1. In what follows, all the congruences are modulo 512 unless otherwise specified. By (3) and (9), we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(8n + 7)q^n \equiv 64 \frac{E(q^2)^{14}}{E(q)^7} = 64 \left(\frac{E(q^6)E(q^9)^2}{E(q^3)E(q^{18})} + q \frac{E(q^{18})^2}{E(q^9)} \right)^7.$$

Picking out those terms in which the power of q is congruent to 1 modulo 3, and applying (10), we can see that

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(8(3n + 1) + 7)q^{3n+1} \\ & \equiv 64 \left(-q \frac{E(q^6)^{16}E(q^9)}{E(q^3)^8E(q^{18})^2} - 3q^4 \frac{E(q^6)^8E(q^{18})^6}{E(q^3)^4E(q^9)^3} - 3q^7 \frac{E(q^{18})^{14}}{E(q^9)^7} \right), \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

then, dividing both sides of (12) by q and replacing q by $q^{1/3}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(24n + 15)q^n \\ & \equiv 64 \left(-\frac{E(q^2)^{16}E(q^3)}{E(q)^8E(q^6)^2} - 3q \frac{E(q^2)^8E(q^6)^6}{E(q)^4E(q^3)^3} - 3q^2 \frac{E(q^6)^{14}}{E(q^3)^7} \right) \\ & = 64 \left(-\frac{E(q^3)}{E(q^6)^2} \left(\frac{E(q^2)^2}{E(q)} \right)^8 - 3q \frac{E(q^6)^6}{E(q^3)^3} \left(\frac{E(q^2)^2}{E(q)} \right)^4 - 3q^2 \frac{E(q^6)^{14}}{E(q^3)^7} \right). \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Next, substituting (9) into (13), and selecting those terms of the form of q^{3n+2} , it turns into

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(24(3n + 2) + 15)q^{3n+2} \\ & \equiv 64 \left(-\frac{E(q^3)}{E(q^6)^2} \left(4q^2 \frac{E(q^6)^{16}}{E(q^3)^8} - 3q^8 \frac{E(q^{18})^{16}}{E(q^9)^8} \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - 3q \frac{E(q^6)^6}{E(q^3)^3} \left(4q \frac{E(q^6)^8}{E(q^3)^4} - 3q^4 \frac{E(q^{18})^8}{E(q^9)^4} \right) - 3q^2 \frac{E(q^6)^{14}}{E(q^3)^7} \right) \\ & \equiv 64 \left(5q^2 \frac{E(q^6)^{14}}{E(q^3)^7} + q^5 \frac{E(q^6)^6E(q^{18})^8}{E(q^3)^3E(q^9)^4} + 3q^8 \frac{E(q^{18})^{16}E(q^3)}{E(q^9)^8E(q^6)^2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

After simplification, we deduce that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(72n + 63)q^n \equiv 64 \left(5 \frac{E(q^2)^{14}}{E(q)^7} + q \frac{E(q^2)^6E(q^6)^8}{E(q)^3E(q^3)^4} + 3q^2 \frac{E(q)E(q^6)^{16}}{E(q^2)^2E(q^3)^8} \right). \tag{14}$$

Applying (9)-(12), picking out those terms of the form of q^{3n+1} , and substituting

(11) into (14), upon simplification, one can arrive at

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(72(3n+1)+63)q^{3n+1} \\ & \equiv 64 \left(4q \frac{E(q^6)^{16}E(q^9)}{E(q^3)^8E(q^{18})^2} + 4q^4 \frac{E(q^6)^8E(q^{18})^6}{E(q^3)^4E(q^9)^3} + q^7 \frac{E(q^{18})^{14}}{E(q^9)^7} \right), \end{aligned}$$

or, equivalently,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(216n+135)q^n \\ & \equiv 64 \left(4 \frac{E(q^2)^{16}E(q^3)}{E(q)^8E(q^6)^2} + 4q \frac{E(q^2)^8E(q^6)^6}{E(q)^4E(q^3)^3} + q^2 \frac{E(q^6)^{14}}{E(q^3)^7} \right) \\ & \equiv 64 \left(4 \frac{E(q^3)}{E(q^6)^2} \left(\frac{E(q^2)^2}{E(q)} \right)^8 + 4q \frac{E(q^6)^6}{E(q^3)^3} \left(\frac{E(q^2)^2}{E(q)} \right)^4 + q^2 \frac{E(q^6)^{14}}{E(q^3)^7} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Following a similar strategy as above, we find that

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(216(3n+2)+135)q^{3n+2} \\ & \equiv 64 \left(4 \frac{E(q^3)}{E(q^6)^2} \left(4q^2 \frac{E(q^6)^{16}}{E(q^3)^8} - 3q^8 \frac{E(q^{18})^{16}}{E(q^9)^8} \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + 4q \frac{E(q^6)^6}{E(q^3)^3} \left(4q \frac{E(q^6)^8}{E(q^3)^4} - 3q^4 \frac{E(q^{18})^8}{E(q^9)^4} \right) + q^2 \frac{E(q^6)^{14}}{E(q^3)^7} \right) \\ & \equiv 64 \left(q^2 \frac{E(q^6)^{14}}{E(q^3)^7} + 4q^5 \frac{E(q^6)^6E(q^{18})^8}{E(q^3)^3E(q^9)^4} + 4q^8 \frac{E(q^3)E(q^{18})^{16}}{E(q^6)^2E(q^9)^8} \right). \end{aligned}$$

That is,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(648n+567)q^n \equiv 64 \left(\frac{E(q^2)^{14}}{E(q)^7} + 4q \frac{E(q^2)^6E(q^6)^8}{E(q)^3E(q^3)^4} + 4q^2 \frac{E(q)E(q^6)^{16}}{E(q^2)^2E(q^3)^8} \right).$$

Utilizing (9)-(12), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(648(3n+1)+567)q^{3n+1} \\ & \equiv 64 \left(3q \frac{E(q^6)^{16}E(q^9)}{E(q^3)^8E(q^{18})^2} + q^4 \frac{E(q^6)^8E(q^{18})^6}{E(q^3)^4E(q^9)^3} - 3q^7 \frac{E(q^{18})^{14}}{E(q^9)^7} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(1944n+1215)q^n \equiv 64 \left(3 \frac{E(q^2)^{16}E(q^3)}{E(q)^8E(q^6)^2} + q \frac{E(q^2)^8E(q^6)^6}{E(q)^4E(q^3)^3} - 3q^2 \frac{E(q^6)^{14}}{E(q^3)^7} \right).$$

In the same vein, we derive that

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(1944(3n+2) + 1215)q^{3n+2} \\ & \equiv 64 \left(-3q^2 \frac{E(q^6)^{14}}{E(q^3)^7} - 3q^5 \frac{E(q^6)^6 E(q^{18})^8}{E(q^3)^3 E(q^9)^4} - q^8 \frac{E(q^3) E(q^{18})^{16}}{E(q^6)^2 E(q^9)^8} \right), \end{aligned}$$

from which we obtain that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(5832n + 5103)q^n \equiv 64 \left(-3 \frac{E(q^2)^{14}}{E(q)^7} - 3q \frac{E(q^2)^6 E(q^6)^8}{E(q)^3 E(q^3)^4} - q^2 \frac{E(q) E(q^6)^{16}}{E(q^2)^2 E(q^3)^8} \right).$$

Using (9), (10), and (12), we further arrive at

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(5832(3n+1) + 5103)q^{3n+1} \equiv 64q^7 \frac{E(q^{18})^{14}}{E(q^9)^7}.$$

It follows that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(17496n + 10935)q^n = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(8 \cdot 3^7 n + 5 \cdot 3^7)q^n \equiv 64q^2 \frac{E(q^6)^{14}}{E(q^3)^7}. \tag{15}$$

Finally,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(17496(3n+2) + 10935)q^n = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(8 \cdot 3^8 n + 7 \cdot 3^8)q^n \equiv 64 \frac{E(q^2)^{14}}{E(q)^7}.$$

Thus, one can obtain that for any $n \geq 0$,

$$\bar{p}(8 \cdot 3^8 n + 7 \cdot 3^8) \equiv \bar{p}(8n + 7). \tag{16}$$

Based on (16) and induction, we can deduce that for any $\alpha \geq 0$,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(8 \cdot 3^{8\alpha} n + 7 \cdot 3^{8\alpha})q^n \equiv \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(8n + 7)q^n \equiv 64 \frac{E(q^2)^{14}}{E(q)^7}. \tag{17}$$

Combining (15) and (17) gives

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(8 \cdot 3^{8\alpha+7} n + 5 \cdot 3^{8\alpha+7})q^n \equiv 64q^2 \frac{E(q^6)^{14}}{E(q^3)^7}. \tag{18}$$

Since there are no terms in which the powers of q are congruent to 0 or 1 modulo 3 on the right-hand side of (18), we readily get

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{p}(8 \cdot 3^{8\alpha+7}(3n) + 5 \cdot 3^{8\alpha+7}) & \equiv 0 \pmod{2^9}, \\ \bar{p}(8 \cdot 3^{8\alpha+7}(3n+1) + 5 \cdot 3^{8\alpha+7}) & \equiv 0 \pmod{2^9}. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

3. Closing Remarks

In this paper, we establish two infinite families of congruences modulo 512 for the overpartition function $\bar{p}(n)$ by utilizing some q -series techniques. Moreover, we conjecture that there exist two infinite families of congruences modulo high powers of s satisfied by $\bar{p}(n)$. Obviously, if (8) is true, then for any $k \geq 1$, the following inequality also holds:

$$\lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\#\{0 \leq n < X : \bar{p}(n) \equiv 0 \pmod{2^k}\}}{X} > 0.$$

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